

Prediction of Wine Quality using KNN Machine Learning Model

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Abstract

Wine quality is of paramount importance in the beverage industry due to its widespread demand and competitive market landscape. Wine quality classification is a difficult task because the assessment given by human experts makes the process very expensive and time consuming. The main aim of this project is to predict wine quality by using K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) machine learning model. The user opens the GUI application, supplies the values of the wine features, the entered information serves as the dataset for the red wine quality prediction system, which utilizes it to accurately forecast outcomes based on the specified range. The output of the KNN algorithm has been estimated using various evaluation metrics. with respect to precision, recall, f1-score and accuracy are 21.277%, 52.632%, 30.303%, and 85.625% respectively. Kaggle red wine dataset serves as a benchmark for the project. The significance of the project is that the adoption of a machine learning model in predicting wine quality can enhance both the efficiency and precision of wine quality evaluations before production.

Keywords: Quality of wine, Red wine, KNN, Classification, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

Wine quality is of paramount importance in the beverage industry due to its widespread demand and competitive market landscape. Ensuring wine quality is crucial for both consumers and producers, prompting the adoption of proactive quality control measures throughout the production

cycle Baheti et al. (2024). The red wine industry is growing at a tremendous speed as more and more people start to drink wine. Therefore, the industry is becoming competitive and wine companies need to make better quality wines to stand out Dong (2023). In America, people spend more than 70 billion dollars on wine every year.

According to Bhardwaj et al. (2022) the wine business relies heavily on wine quality certification. The production of wine due to excessive consumption has increased in modern times. In most parts of the world wine consumption is a trend due to social and normative factors Kumar et al. (2020) as cited in Gawale, (2022). The increased production of wine has been the key factor behind the huge market competition. Most wine producing companies are facing enormous challenges to justify their wine quality. To maintain wine quality, companies are bound to focus on wine certification to assess wine quality within the market Cardoso et al. (2022). According to Pradnya et al. (2023) drinking low-quality wine has a negative effect on one's health, wine quality is particularly important. Wine quality is one of the most significant issues in the wine industry. Quality is defined by the person who defines it, regardless of whether they are an expert or not. The chemical makeup of the wine determines the wine's flavour, fragrance, colour, and other characteristics. The chemical composition is influenced by the grape type, environmental circumstances, microbial strains present during fermentation, and viticulture practises (Bhardwaj et al., 2022). The introduction of technology has brought machine learning, deep learning, and hybrid techniques to predict wine quality and increase the accuracy ratio Baheti et al. (2024).

2. Statement of Problem

Wine quality is determined by the ingredients that go into its production. Wine is a popular drink across the globe, the older the wine, the better is the taste but, expensive. The wine quality is measured based on the important parameters, such as free Sulphur dioxide, Volatile acidity, Citric

Acid and Residual sugar Saranya et al. (2024). Wine quality depends on several stages, nowadays, industries are using product quality certifications to promote their products (Gupta, 2017). This is a time taking process and requires the assessment given by human experts which makes this process very expensive and time consuming. The traditional way of wine quality assessment is time consuming. Also, from the literature reviewed, the researchers that made use of machine learning, implemented their code which provides less GUI user interaction. For buyers and the wine business to produce in sufficient amounts, wine quality is crucial. Wine quality classification is a difficult task because taste is the least important of the five senses Pradnya et al. (2023). To nearly accurately forecasting wine quality presents a significant challenge within the wine industry, hence, this is a research gap whereby this project will explore the usage of machine learning model to predict wine quality alongside graphical user interface library to enhance user interaction.

3. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim in this project is to predict wine quality by using machine learning model.

The objectives are:

- i. Collection of dataset that consist of red wine features
- ii. Design a web application for wine quality prediction
- iii. implement machine learning algorithm in (ii) using Python
- iv. evaluate the model performance in (iii) using wine classification accuracy, precision, f1_score, and recall.

4. Literature Review

Many researchers published related works on wine prediction. From this background, this section provides an overview on some of the main studies conducted on different data to predict wine quality using machine learning:

In Bhardwaj et al. (2022), the authors predict wine quality by generating synthetic data and construct a machine learning model based on this synthetic data and available experimental data collected from different and diverse regions across New Zealand. They utilised 18 Pinot noir wine samples with 54 different characteristics (7 physiochemical and 47 chemical features). They generated 1381 samples from 12 original samples using the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) method, and six samples were preserved for model testing. The findings were compared using four distinct feature selection approaches. Seven machine learning algorithms were trained and tested on a holdout original sample. Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) classifier showed 100% accuracy when trained and evaluated without feature selection.

In Gupta (2018), the author explores the usage of machine learning techniques for product quality by using linear regression to determine the dependency of target variable on independent variables. On the basis of computed dependency, important variables are selected. Further, neural network and support vector machine are used to predict the values of dependent variable. All the experiments are performed on Red wine and White wine datasets. This paper proves that the better prediction can be made if selected features (variables) are being considered rather than considering all the features.

In Saranya et al. (2024), the authors' project gives an automatic prediction of Wine quality, as good or bad, using machine learning approaches which are Neural Networks, Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine are implemented on datasets of Portuguese “Vinho Verde” Wine. The results are compared with standard values. The work is useful in Wine industry for quality testing and assurance for customers.

Baheti et al. (2024), the authors' paper investigates the predictive modeling of alcohol quality machine learning regression analysis. The study employs a comprehensive approach to preprocessing, modeling, and evaluation to achieve accurate predictions. Overall, this paper

demonstrates the effectiveness of linear regression in predicting alcohol content with an accuracy of 92%, offering valuable implications for quality control and production optimization in the alcohol industry along with other regression models such as gradient boosting with an accuracy of 90% and decision tree regressor with an accuracy of 83%.

In Dong (2023), the author used machine learning techniques to analyze 1599 wine samples each with 11 input variables in order to find the variables that have the most impact on wine's general quality. The linear regression model used in the paper shows the most influential variables on quality are alcohol and acid. In addition, a heat map was adopted to show all the correlation between the variables. To go deeper, box plot and 3D scatter plot were used to support the finding through linear regression model and have a more detailed conclusion on the variables that have the most impact on quality. These results shed light on what are the most influential variables on wine's quality.

5. Proposed Methodology

According to Irfan et al. (2019), Classification is a supervised learning process. Classification is defined as a form of data analysis to extract a model that will be used to predict class labels. This project utilized the K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) algorithm, a type of supervised machine learning model. The research was structured around an experimental framework and web development that involved gathering a dataset, specifically by leveraging publicly accessible datasets related to wine. The process commenced with the importation of the wine dataset, followed by data pre-processing and feature extraction. KNN algorithm was then employed to establish the classification task after dividing the dataset into training and testing subsets. Finally, the model was assessed to evaluate the impact of the optimization on its performance.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the methodology

We downloaded a dataset of 1500+ wine samples from the Kaggle Machine Learning Repository, which has become very famous as an open-source dataset. In this dataset there are 1599 records, each record contains 11 different features of wine. The dataset consists of 1599 rows and 12 columns, the 12th column handles the prediction class. This analysis focuses exclusively on red wine. The output variable represents quality, which is scored between 0 and 10.

	fixed acidity	volatile acidity	citric acid	...	sulphates	alcohol	quality
0	7.4	0.70	0.00	...	0.56	9.4	5
1	7.8	0.88	0.00	...	0.68	9.8	5
2	7.8	0.76	0.04	...	0.65	9.8	5
3	11.2	0.28	0.56	...	0.58	9.8	6
4	7.4	0.70	0.00	...	0.56	9.4	5
5	7.4	0.66	0.00	...	0.56	9.4	5
6	7.9	0.60	0.06	...	0.46	9.4	5
7	7.3	0.65	0.00	...	0.47	10.0	7
8	7.8	0.58	0.02	...	0.57	9.5	7
9	7.5	0.50	0.36	...	0.80	10.5	5

[10 rows x 12 columns]

Figure 2: Screenshot sample of red wine dataset

Table 1: Features of the Dataset (Author, 2025)

S/N	Features (column name)	datatype
1	Fixed acidity	float
2	Volatile acidity	Float
3	Citric acid	Float
4	Residual sugar	Float
5	Chlorides	Float
6	Free sulfur dioxide	Float
7	Total sulfur dioxide	Float
8	Density	Float
9	pH	Float
10	Sulphates	Float
11	Alcohol	Float
12	Prediction quality	Integer

6. Algorithm

KNN is a classification method that determines the label (class) of a new object based on the class that is a majority from k-neighbour in the training set. KNN is a classification algorithm based on analogy, which compares testing data with training data that are close to and have similarities to the test data. The KNN algorithm is a method for classifying objects based on learning data that are closest to the object. Learning data is projected to be a multi-dimensional space, where each dimension represents the features of the data. This space divided into sections based on the classification of learning data. A point in this space is marked with class c, if class c is the classification that most often found in the k-neighbour of the closest to that point. KNN is a supervised method, where the results of querying new instances classified according to the majority of categories on the KNN. In the training phase, this algorithm only stores feature vectors and classifications of training sample data. In the classification phase, the same features calculated for data testing (the classification is unknown). The distance from this new vector to all sample training vectors calculated, and the closest k will taken. The new point of classification that is

already predicted to included in the most classification of these points (Irfan et al., 2019). The Equation below is used to calculate the similarity of the data in k-neighbour.

$$\text{Similarity } (T, S) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Sim}(K_i(T), K_i(S)) x w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w}$$

Where:

T = testing data

S = training data

n = total of criteria

w = weight of criteria

Sim (K_i(T), K_i(S)) = Similarity value or criteria distance between case target and source target

Working of KNN algorithm

The 'K' here in K-NN refers to the count of neighbors of the new data point. Deciding a suitable value for K is the foremost process in this algorithm. For better accuracy, it is imperative that one chooses the accurate value of K, and this process is called parameter tuning. A very low value of K like 1 or 2 can lead to noisy results, whereas, a very high value can create confusion at times, depending on the data set. There is no fixed value for K, however, one of the standard values that K often assumes is '5' i.e., for the majority voting process, the 5 neighbors closest to the new data point are considered. To avoid mistakes and confusion among two classes of data sets, generally, an odd value of K is suitable (Bansal et al. 2022). Another formula-based calculation for K can be done through this formula:

$$K = \sqrt{n}$$

And, n is the overall count of data points.

Figure 3: Schematic of KNN for Classification of new data point based on neighbors (a) (Bansal et al. 2022).

Figure 4: Schematic of KNN to find Euclidean Distance between two points (Bansal et al. 2022).

3.2.1.1 Implementation of KNN

KNN is used to identify patterns and relationships in features. Lastly we train and test the model.

The algorithm for wine quality prediction is as follows:

Step1: Import libraries (numpy and pandas)

Step2: Load kaggle data set

Step3: Separate dataset into features and labels

Step4: Split data for testing (20% and training 80%)

Step5: Perform normalization

Step6: Train KNN classifier

Step7: Check efficiency for evaluation of model

7. Result and Discussion

The implementation of the system involves the development of a new application based on the strategies outlined in the preceding chapter and the designated implementation environment. This chapter illustrates the execution of the plan, with the objective of delivering a system that utilizes machine learning to predict wine quality.

Model evaluation metrics

Consequently, on the selected dataset, we assess and validate the performance of the selected algorithm KNN by using four evaluation metrics: accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

Accuracy

Accuracy is a true prediction ratio (positive and negative) by testing the entire data into the model to obtain the target value. Accuracy is used to find the amount of data classified correctly Anggoro

& Kurnia (2020). Algorithm performance in terms of accuracy can be evaluated using the formula below:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + FP + FN + TN)} * 100\%$$

Where:

TP = True Positive

TN = True Negative

FP = False Positive

FN = False Negative

F1-score

The F-score is defined as the weighted average of both precision and recall depending on the weight function β , see Formula below:.. The F1-score means the harmonic mean between precision and recall, when it is written F-score it usually means F1-score. The F-score is also called the F-measure. The F1-score can have different indices giving different weights to precision and recall (Dalianis, 2018).

$$\text{F-score} : F_{\beta} = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{P * R}{\beta^2 * P + R}$$

With $\beta= 1$ the standard F-score is obtained

$$\text{F1 - Score} = \frac{2T_P}{2T_P + F_p + F_N} \times 100$$

Recall

Recall measures the number of correct instances retrieved divided by all correct instances (Dalianis, 2018), see the Formula below:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{T_P}{T_P + F_N} \times 100$$

Precision

Precision measures the number of correct instances retrieved divided by all retrieved instances (Dalianis, 2018), see the Formula below:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{T_P}{T_P + F_P} \times 100$$

Table 2: Model Evaluation

	K-Nearest Neighbor
Precision	21.277%
Recall	52.632%
F1 Score	30.303%
Accuracy	85.625%

Regarding the accuracy metric, it indicates that 85.625% of the total predictions, encompassing both correct positives and negatives, made by the model were accurate. In terms of the precision metric, it reveals the proportion of wines classified as 'good quality' that were indeed of good quality. The recall metric assesses the model's capability to identify all actual good quality wines, with a recall rate of 52.632% signifying that it accurately recognizes approximately half of the good quality wines. Lastly, the F1-score metric, with a score of 30.3%, demonstrates a significant imbalance between precision and recall, primarily influenced by the low precision.

Figure 5: Screenshot of Wine_Quality_Prediction Page

The above screenshot illustrates the web page where all essential data is entered for evaluation, leading to the generation of corresponding results. The entered information through the left sliders serves as the dataset for the red wine quality prediction system, which utilizes it to accurately forecast outcomes based on the specified range.

8. Conclusion

The main aim in this project is to predict wine quality by using machine learning model. This project utilized the K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) algorithm, a type of supervised machine learning model. The research was structured around an experimental framework that involved gathering a dataset, specifically by leveraging Kaggle publicly accessible datasets related to wine.

The result obtained in the implementation shows that when all essential data is entered by the user for evaluation, leading to the generation of corresponding results. The entered information serves as the dataset for the red wine quality prediction system, which utilizes it to accurately forecast outcomes based on the specified range. The application then analyzes these inputs to predict the

quality of red wine, categorizing values from 0 to 3 as low quality, 4 to 6 as average quality, and 7 to 10 as high quality, as indicated in the prediction table.

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